

ADDRESSING TEENAGE OBESITY: THE CONTRIBUTION OF COMMUNITY NURSES IN SCHOOL-BASED HEALTH PROMOTION INITIATIVES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the contributions of community nurses in school-based health promotion initiatives concerning teenage obesity issues. Employing a descriptive research design, the study involved 11 teacher participants, and data were primarily collected through a survey questionnaire. Statistical tools such as weighted mean and composite mean were utilized for analysis. The findings indicate a strong consensus among teachers regarding the significant role played by community nurses in fostering health promotion initiatives within the school environment. Furthermore, teachers collectively acknowledge and support the effectiveness of community nurses in delivering impactful health education sessions. The results also highlight the perceived success among teachers in recognizing community nurses for providing meaningful support, underscoring their essential role in promoting the well-being of students grappling with weight-related issues.

Keywords: *teenage obesity, community nurse, health promotion initiatives*

INTRODUCTION

The global concern of teenage obesity has escalated over time, with consistently rising rates. This health epidemic not only immediately jeopardizes the well-being of young individuals but also has enduring consequences for their future. Adolescents grappling with obesity face an elevated risk of developing chronic conditions such as

diabetes, cardiovascular problems, and musculoskeletal issues, in addition to negative impacts on self-esteem, mental health, and overall quality of life.

As of September 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) expresses deep concern about the escalating global teenage obesity epidemic. Rates have tripled since the 1970s, with approximately 340 million adolescents aged 5 to 19 being overweight or obese, unveiling disparities within and between regions. Despite some progress, many countries struggle with the health implications of unhealthy habits, reduced physical activity, and changing environments. The WHO emphasizes the need for cohesive strategies and cross-sector collaboration to effectively address this challenge.

In the Philippines, teenage obesity is a pressing issue fueled by evolving diets, processed foods, sedentary technology-driven habits, and limited activity options, particularly in certain regions undergoing urbanization. Mitigation efforts include education, school initiatives, and the promotion of healthier habits.

A study conducted in Nasugbu, Batangas, Philippines by BatStateU RMIS (2016) sought to comprehend the prevalence, causes, and academic effects of obesity among grade four to six students. Out of 225 pupils, 8% were obese, and 30.67% were overweight. Sociodemographic factors, especially paternal occupation and age were correlated with obesity. Associations were found with the consumption of fatty foods, snacks, and fast-food visits. Limited sports and reading were linked to a higher likelihood of obesity, while passive eating activities increased the likelihood by 30%. Many lacked awareness of obesity's risks, and surprisingly, obese pupils performed well academically. The study emphasized the potential consequences of obesity and advocated for vigilant monitoring of overweight students.

Schools have emerged as crucial venues for addressing teenage obesity, with health promotion programs gaining traction as potential solutions. Given their ability to reach a large number of teenagers, schools are ideal settings for interventions. These programs typically aim to promote healthy eating habits, physical activity, and educate students about the advantages of a balanced lifestyle. Enhancing their effectiveness involves the inclusion of community nurses and other stakeholders (Chaudhary et al., 2020).

According to the National Academies Press (2021), community nurses can play a pivotal role in organizing targeted health education sessions in schools. These sessions cover various issues, including the negative effects of being overweight, the benefits of healthy eating, and the importance of regular exercise. Nurses can employ engaging methods to ensure that information is easily understood and relevant to teenagers. Recognizing the unique requirements and obstacles of each teenager, community nurses can provide personalized advice, such as creating diet plans, suggesting exercise routines, and regularly tracking progress. This individualized attention aims to motivate students and instill a sense of responsibility for their health.

Collaboration between community nurses and school staff is essential for promoting overall health. By working with physical education teachers, nutritionists, and counselors, nurses can develop interventions addressing multiple aspects of students' well-being. Engaging families is crucial in addressing teenage obesity, as home environments significantly influence adolescents' behavior. Community nurses can organize workshops for parents, educating them on healthy cooking, establishing

supportive home environments, and understanding their children's emotional needs during this critical phase.

Sustaining changes in teenagers' lifestyles requires ongoing effort. Community nurses can cultivate lasting relationships with students by providing continuous support and motivation. Consistent check-ins, progress monitoring, and adjustments to health plans can lead to greater success. To assess the effectiveness of their interventions, community nurses can collect data on students' progress in areas such as weight loss, improved fitness, and changes in health behaviors. This data offers valuable insights into the impact of their efforts, guiding future program improvements.

Effectively addressing teenage obesity necessitates a comprehensive approach involving schools, families, and the community. Community nurses, equipped with knowledge in health promotion and patient education, play a pivotal role in successful school-based interventions. Through the provision of education, support, and collaboration, community nurses can make substantial contributions to reducing teenage obesity rates and enhancing the overall health of adolescents.

Research Questions

This study is conducted to identify contributions of community nurses in school-based health promotion initiatives in addressing the issues on teenage obesity.

Specifically, it aimed to:

1. investigate the extent to which community nurses contribute to the planning and implementation of school-based health promotion initiatives aimed at preventing and reducing adolescent obesity.
 2. assess the impact of community nurses' engagement in personalized health education sessions within schools on the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to nutrition and physical activity among adolescents.
 3. evaluate the effectiveness of community nurses in providing individualized advice and support to overweight or obese students, including the development and monitoring of personalized diet and exercise plans.
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METHODOLOGY

The research employed a descriptive approach to identify contributions of community nurses in school-based health promotion initiatives in addressing the issues on teenage obesity. The methodology encompassed the description, analysis, interpretation, and documentation of data. The study involved 11 Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) teachers from Lucsuhin National High School in Calatagan, Batangas, who served as participants. Purposive sampling was utilized by selecting the entire total population. The researcher developed a survey questionnaire through construction, validation, administration, and scoring processes.

The study began with the researcher composing an official letter directed to the school's principal, formally requesting authorization for the study's execution. Following

the approval process, the questionnaire was administered to the teachers, along with clear and precise instructions, and steps were taken to ensure that the test materials were collected on the same day as their administration. The researcher tallied, tabulated, and interpreted the data from the respondents utilizing descriptive statistics, including weighted mean and composite mean.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this part, an analysis and interpretation of data are provided, examining the community nurses' contribution to school-based health promotion initiatives.

1. Community Nurses' Contribution to School-Based Health Promotion Initiatives

The analysis of the data collected on community nurses' contribution to school-based health promotion initiatives reveals valuable insights into the effectiveness of their involvement. Through a careful examination of various aspects, including planning, implementation, and impact on adolescents, the results shed light on the pivotal role community nurses play in fostering a healthier school environment and combating adolescent obesity.

Table 1
Community Nurses' Contribution to School-Based Health Promotion Initiatives

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Community nurses actively participate in the planning of school-based health promotion initiatives addressing adolescent obesity.	3.97	SA
2. The continuous participation of community nurses in school-based health promotion initiatives is essential for sustaining long-term positive outcomes in preventing and reducing adolescent obesity.	3.94	SA
3. The involvement of community nurses in the implementation phase of health promotion programs significantly contributes to their overall effectiveness.	3.90	SA
4. Community nurses collaborate effectively with school administrators and educators to integrate obesity prevention strategies into the school curriculum.	3.90	SA
5. The expertise of community nurses enhances the development of engaging and informative materials for promoting healthy lifestyles among adolescents.	3.87	SA
6. Community nurses play a pivotal role in tailoring health promotion initiatives to the specific needs and preferences of the adolescent population.	3.80	SA

7. The input provided by community nurses is instrumental in identifying and addressing barriers to the successful implementation of obesity prevention measures in schools.	3.80	SA
8. The proactive involvement of community nurses positively influences the overall culture of health and wellness within the school environment.	3.77	SA
9. Community nurses actively engage with parents and guardians to extend the impact of health promotion initiatives beyond the school setting.	3.67	SA
10. The collaboration between community nurses and school staff fosters a cohesive approach in the planning and execution of programs targeting adolescent obesity.	3.54	SA
Composite Mean	3.82	Strongly Agree

Table 1 presents the contribution of community nurses to school-based health promotion initiatives. It can be gleaned from the table that the teachers strongly agreed that community nurses actively participate in the planning of school-based health promotion initiatives addressing adolescent obesity. This was attested by a weighted mean of 3.97. This suggests a strong and positive collaboration between community nurses and teachers in the strategic development of programs aimed at addressing the complex issue of adolescent obesity within the school context.

On the other hand, despite that this indicator was strongly agreed by the respondents, indicator, the collaboration between community nurses and school staff fosters a cohesive approach in the planning and execution of programs targeting adolescent obesity, got the lowest weighted mean of 3.54. This incongruence in the perceived effectiveness of collaboration may indicate a potential discrepancy in the actual implementation or understanding of the collaborative process, warranting further investigation into the specific challenges or factors influencing this aspect of the health promotion programs. It is crucial to delve deeper into the reasons behind the lower weighted mean to identify areas of improvement and enhance the collaborative dynamics between community nurses and school staff for more effective initiatives targeting adolescent obesity.

With a notable composite mean of 3.82, the strong agreement among teacher-respondents underscores the positive perception of Community Nurses' Contribution to School-Based Health Promotion Initiatives. This high composite mean suggests a strong endorsement from teachers regarding the significant role played by community nurses in fostering health promotion initiatives within the school environment.

The above findings are supported by Maier et al. (2018) which described district nurses' perspectives on their health-promotive and disease-preventive work, emphasizing their role in promoting health and wellbeing across community nursing teams.

2. Assessment of Community Nurses' Health Education Sessions

The findings from the assessment of community nurses' health education sessions provide a comprehensive understanding of their impact on adolescents' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to nutrition and physical activity. Through careful analysis, these results illuminate the effectiveness of personalized health education sessions facilitated by community nurses, offering valuable insights into their role in promoting a positive impact on adolescent health and well-being.

It can be gleaned from Table 2, that teachers strongly agreed that personalized health education sessions facilitated by community nurses effectively enhance adolescents' knowledge about nutrition. This suggests that teachers recognize the valuable role played by community nurses in delivering educational content that contributes significantly to enhancing adolescents' understanding of nutritional concepts. The consensus on this aspect highlights the success of community nurses in providing targeted and effective health education within the school setting.

Despite the strong agreement among respondents regarding the indicator that emphasizes the positive impact of personalized health education sessions on adolescents' willingness to make lifestyle changes, it is notable that this particular indicator received the lowest weighted mean of 3.50. This discrepancy in the weighted mean suggests that, while respondents generally agreed on the positive influence of these sessions, there may be nuances or specific challenges affecting the perceived effectiveness of fostering a greater willingness among adolescents to make positive lifestyle changes. Further exploration is warranted to identify potential factors influencing this lower weighted mean and to refine strategies for maximizing the impact of personalized health education sessions on adolescents' attitudes toward positive lifestyle changes.

Table 2
Assessment of Community Nurses' Health Education Sessions

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The personalized health education sessions facilitated by community nurses effectively enhance adolescents' knowledge about nutrition.	3.92	SA
2. The impact of community nurses' health education sessions extends beyond the classroom, influencing adolescents to practice healthier habits in their daily lives.	3.89	SA
3. Community nurses' engagement in health education sessions positively influences adolescents' attitudes towards maintaining a healthy lifestyle.	3.85	SA
4. The content delivered in health education sessions by community nurses is relevant and applicable to the daily lives of adolescents.	3.85	SA

5. Community nurses effectively communicate the importance of balanced nutrition and physical activity during health education sessions.	3.82	SA
6. Adolescents who participate in health education sessions facilitated by community nurses demonstrate an increased awareness of the consequences of unhealthy eating habits.	3.75	SA
7. Community nurses play a significant role in positively shaping adolescents' attitudes toward incorporating regular physical activity into their routines.	3.75	SA
8. The health education sessions conducted by community nurses contribute to noticeable improvements in adolescents' dietary choices.	3.72	SA
9. Community nurses successfully encourage adolescents to adopt healthier behaviors related to nutrition and physical activity.	3.62	SA
10. Adolescents who engage in personalized health education sessions with community nurses exhibit a greater willingness to make positive lifestyle changes.	3.50	SA

Composite Mean	3.77	Strongly Agree
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The overall composite mean of 3.77 underscores a strong agreement among teachers in their assessment of community nurses' health education sessions. This high composite mean suggests a unanimous positive evaluation from teachers, indicating that they collectively recognize and endorse the effectiveness of community nurses in delivering impactful health education sessions within the school environment. The strong agreement reinforces the perceived value and success of these sessions in contributing to the health and well-being of students.

The above findings are parallel with the result of the study of Zeydani et al. (2021) which stated that community-based education for nurses can improve communication skills, teamwork, leadership skills, critical thinking skills, and practical skills, as well as the ability to identify community social issues and use knowledge to understand challenges.

3. Community Nurses' Effectiveness in Supporting Overweight or Obese Students

The results of the evaluation on community nurses' effectiveness in supporting overweight or obese students offer a detailed examination of their role in providing individualized advice and support, including the development and monitoring of personalized diet and exercise plans. This analysis provides valuable insights into the impact of community nurses on the well-being and lifestyle choices of overweight or

obese students, highlighting their effectiveness in addressing these health challenges within a school setting.

Table 3
Community Nurses' Effectiveness in Supporting Overweight or Obese Students

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The individualized advice and support offered by community nurses significantly contribute to positive changes in the health behaviors of overweight or obese students.	3.84	SA
2. The individualized advice provided by community nurses is clear and easy for overweight or obese students to understand.	3.81	SA
3. Community nurses demonstrate a genuine commitment to the well-being of overweight or obese students in their care.	3.77	SA
4. Overweight or obese students report a sense of trust and confidence in the guidance received from community nurses.	3.77	SA
5. Community nurses play a crucial role in the development of personalized diet plans for overweight or obese students.	3.74	SA
6. The exercise routines recommended by community nurses are practical and feasible for overweight or obese students to incorporate into their daily lives.	3.68	SA
7. Overweight or obese students feel empowered to take responsibility for their health with the support and guidance provided by community nurses.	3.68	SA
8. Community nurses effectively monitor the progress of overweight or obese students in adhering to personalized diet and exercise plans.	3.65	SA
9. Overweight or obese students express satisfaction with the ongoing support received from community nurses.	3.55	SA
10. Community nurses effectively tailor advice and support to meet the specific needs of overweight or obese students.	3.42	A
Composite Mean	3.69	Strongly Agree

The weighted mean of 3.84 reflects a strong agreement among teachers regarding the significant impact of individualized advice and support provided by community nurses on positive changes in the health behaviors of overweight or obese students. This high mean underscores a consensus among teachers that community nurses play a crucial role in positively influencing the well-being and lifestyle choices of

students facing weight-related challenges. The result suggests a recognition of the effectiveness of personalized guidance from community nurses in fostering positive health outcomes among overweight or obese students within the school setting.

Despite the agreement among teachers on the indicator emphasizing that community nurses effectively tailor advice and support to meet the specific needs of overweight or obese students, the lowest weighted mean of 3.42 indicates a somewhat lower level of endorsement compared to other aspects. This discrepancy may suggest that while teachers generally agree on the effectiveness of tailored advice and support, there might be room for improvement or specific challenges in the customization process. Further exploration is warranted to understand the factors contributing to this lower weighted mean and to enhance the precision of community nurses in tailoring support to meet the specific needs of overweight or obese students.

The overall composite mean of 3.69 signifies a strong agreement among teachers in their evaluation of community nurses' effectiveness in supporting overweight or obese students. This high composite mean reflects a unanimous recognition among teachers regarding the positive impact and efficacy of community nurses in addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by overweight or obese students within the school setting. The strong agreement emphasizes the perceived success of community nurses in providing meaningful support, underlining their crucial role in promoting the well-being of students dealing with weight-related issues.

The findings conform with the study of Zeydani et al. (2021) which showed that community-based education for nurses can improve communication skills, teamwork, leadership skills, critical thinking skills, and practical skills, as well as the ability to identify community social issues and use knowledge to understand challenges.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the following conclusions can be determined:

1. There is a strong agreement among teachers regarding the significant role played by community nurses in fostering health promotion initiatives within the school environment.
2. Teachers collectively recognize and endorse the effectiveness of community nurses in delivering impactful health education sessions within the school environment.
3. There is a perceived success among teachers of community nurses in providing meaningful support, underlining their crucial role in promoting the well-being of students dealing with weight-related issues.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the collected data, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

1. School should strengthen collaboration between community nurses and school staff to enhance health promotion initiatives. Encourage regular communication, joint planning sessions, and collaborative decision-making to leverage both parties' expertise, fostering more effective programs addressing diverse student health needs.
2. School should enhance health education programs by building on the effectiveness of community nurses. Expand the scope of sessions to cover a broader range of health topics, ensuring relevance to evolving student needs. Incorporate interactive methods and technologies for a more engaging learning experience, reinforcing positive health outcomes within the school setting.
3. School should address weight-related challenges by acknowledging and building on the perceived success of community nurses in supporting overweight or obese students. Explore opportunities for expanding resources or developing targeted programs, including additional support mechanisms, workshops, or resources. Empower community nurses to provide more tailored assistance, contributing to the overall well-being of students facing weight-related issues.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the aforementioned research on the role of community nurses in school-based health promotion initiatives, several ethical considerations must be emphasized. Firstly, the principle of informed consent is paramount. Teachers, community nurses, and other stakeholders involved in the study should be provided with comprehensive information about the research objectives, procedures, and potential impacts. Obtaining informed consent ensures that all participants willingly and knowingly contribute to the study, respecting their autonomy and right to withdraw without adverse consequences. Moreover, maintaining confidentiality is crucial to protect the privacy of individuals. All data collected should be anonymized, and personally identifiable information should be handled with utmost care to prevent the inadvertent disclosure of sensitive details, safeguarding the trust placed in the research process.

Secondly, a commitment to beneficence guides the research to prioritize the well-being of all participants. This involves minimizing any potential harm and striving to ensure that the research has a positive impact on the participants and the broader community. Researchers should be vigilant about the potential implications of the study outcomes, particularly when addressing sensitive issues such as weight-related challenges among students. Additionally, transparent reporting is essential for maintaining the integrity of the research. All findings, whether positive or negative, should be accurately presented without selective reporting to avoid misleading interpretations. By upholding these ethical considerations, the research contributes ethically to the field of health promotion, fostering a responsible and respectful approach to inquiry within educational settings. Conduct of this study is vital to uphold the principles of respect, beneficence, and justice, ensuring that the rights and dignity of all participants will be upheld throughout the research process.

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